

**POSITION PAPER: GEOENVIRONMENTAL PRESERVATION
AND YOUTH EMPOWERMENT**

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1. DECLARATION

We, Youth delegates representing the 275,000 youth of Mauritius, united in our commitment to environmental stewardship and sustainable development through sports, hereby declare our vision for 2030:

We acknowledge that our island nation is confronted with existential threats to our very existence in the form of climate change and the projected sea level rise of up to 0.7 m by 2100 will affect 26.2 % of our beaches and 3.5 % of our wetlands (Mauritius Third National Communication to UNFCCC, 2022).

We acknowledge that while sports generate 1% of our national emissions, they can influence 1.3 million Mauritians and 1.4 million tourists (Tourism Statistics Mauritius, 2023).

In exercising our inalienable right to a sustainable future as guaranteed in the Mauritian Constitution and as supported by our commitment under the Paris Agreement.

We demand that our government, sports organizations, and all stakeholders join us in realizing the following non-negotiable goals by 2030:

On Climate Action: We will require that 100% of Mauritian sporting events and facilities are carbon neutral by 2030, consistent with our national target to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2030. We also insist that all national sports teams receive thorough climate resilience training so that they can be ambassadors of climate action.

On Biodiversity and Ecosystems: But we believe that sports activities should be actively pursuing the increase in our forest cover from 25 percent to 35 percent by 2030. And we demand our 50+ sports federations adopt and restore a specific ecosystem, one which is based on our own native flora and fauna, including the Echo Parakeet and the Pink Pigeon.

On Sustainable Resource Management: Mauritius' aim of 60% renewable energy on the national grid by 2030 and our ambition for our sports sector to be powered by 100% renewable energy by 2030. We aim for all sports facilities to achieve zero waste to landfill as part of a national target of 70% waste recycling by 2030.

On Education and Capacity Building: We are demanding that environmental education from 100 hours be integrated into all sports curricula every year, reaching with 100,000 young athletes. We propose the creation of a national center of excellence in sustainable sports management at the University of Mauritius and to train 5,000 youth leaders by 2030.

On Governance and Policy: We also call for the National Sports Council and all sports federation boards to be made up of half youth. By 2025, we call on the Mauritian Government to bring into force a Mauritian Sustainable Sports Act with legally binding targets and enforcement mechanisms.

On Sustainable Tourism and Events: Mauritius still sees itself as a global leader in sustainable sports tourism, whose contribution to GDP should grow from 8% to 15% in 2030 without worsening carbon emissions. Additionally, we have asked that 100% of international sports events hosted in Mauritius, including the Indian Ocean Island Games, meet Global Sustainable Tourism Council criteria.

On Health and Well-being: We link environmental and human health, advocating for sports initiatives that will reduce non communicable diseases that currently represent 80 percent of all deaths in Mauritius and improve our coastal and marine ecosystem services by 30 percent.

On Research and Innovation: We are calling for a 200 per cent increase in funding for environmental sports research at the Mauritius Research and Innovation Council, 100 youth led innovations by 2030. We call for the establishment of a Mauritian Environmental Sports Data Observatory to underpin national climate policy.

On Economic Sustainability: By 2030 we expect a green sports economy to create 10,000 sustainable jobs in Mauritius, and 50% of sports related businesses to be certified SME Mauritius Green.

On International Cooperation: Mauritius is now a global leader in sustainable island sports, partnered with 20 international organizations and our voice is influencing 50% of international sports and environmental policies affecting Small Island Developing States.

The youth of Mauritius commit ourselves to being at the forefront of this transformation. We promise to provide our energy, creativity and passion to the realization of this vision.

Our elders, our leaders, and our global partners must live up to our commitment and match it with bold action, wise governance and unwavering support, knowing that the cost of inaction is far greater than the investment needed to realize this vision.

According to the principle of intergenerational equity, we assert our right to inherit a Mauritius as bountiful as that of our predecessors. We want to work with you, but just as prepared to call out those who don't.

Let us, together, build a future where sports do not just inspire the Mauritian spirit, but the environment itself that we survive in. Mauritius should become a beacons of hope, showing the rest of the world how a tiny island country can lead the world in sustainable sports.

This is our declaration, our vision, and the absolute non-negotiable imperative on our future work. The time for action is now. We are the eyes of the world, and the eyes of future generations.

A unanimous adoption by the Mauritius Youth Ambassadors

Supported by:

H.E Eddy Boisezon Vice President of the Republic of Mauritius
Hon. Stephane Toussaint, Minister of Youth Empowerment, Sports & Recreation
H.E Lisa Singh, UN Resident Coordinator
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2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 About This Statement

As a collective effort, this position paper addresses the critical intersection of youth empowerment, sports engagement and environmental conservation within CJSOI member states. Developed through extensive research, consultation and collaboration with youth leaders, environmental scientists, sports administrators and policy experts across the Indian Ocean region, this emerged. This document seeks to create a dynamic framework from where the strength of sports can be harnessed to ensure environmental stewardship and resilience of the youth of the CJSOI states.

The urgency of this initiative cannot be overstated. Against this backdrop, small island developing states (SIDS) are on the frontlines of the crisis afflicting the planet with climate change. Rich in biodiversity, unique ecosystems and vibrant cultures, CJSOI member states are among the most at risk from rising sea levels, more intense tropical cyclones and destruction of marine and terrestrial habitats. For environmental conservation and climate adaptation, this is novel and possibly transformative, an opportunity to transform engagement of the youth through sports.

Based on existing regional initiatives and global best practices, this position paper is a synthesis of these policy instruments into a policy framework developed in light of the specific needs and opportunities of the CJSOI region. We aim for a generation of sports leaders, physically active, mentally resilient and dedicated to the preservation of their natural heritage that through the integration of environmental education and the practice of sustainable sports program.

2.2 The Global Climate Context of the CJSOI

It constitutes the only global climate component that is the Commission de la Jeunesse et des Sports de l'Océan Indien. The CJSOI is composed of island nations and territories including Comoros, Madagascar, Mauritius, Mayotte, Réunion and Seychelles, an archipelago microcosm of SIDS' challenges and opportunities. Geographically proximate but united in their vulnerability to climate change impacts and collective potential for innovative, youth-driven solutions, these islands create a unity that brings together islands in the western Indian Ocean.

In its assessment reports, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has always pointed out that SIDS were facing the most disproportionate risks. Many of these islands could be rendered uninhabitable within a century, without profound global mitigation action as well as local adaptive capacity, according to the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). This translates for the CJSOI states to a set of immediate and long term threats such as coastal inundation, freshwater scarcity and loss of biodiversity with impactful effects on key economic sectors including tourism and fisheries.

Monitoring the CJSOI region for sustainable development and climate resilience, however, also reveals a global climate context which offers opportunities for such a leadership role. The national determined contributions (NDCs) and the global stocktake are a framework for SIDS to voice their challenging distinctiveness and showcase of innovative ones. Furthermore, the CJSOI states are at par with the increasing global trend on the nature based solutions and blue economy agenda.

In this global context, the matter of the role played by youth and sports is of special note. The success of the UNFCCC in recognizing the critical importance of youth engagement through initiatives like Action for Climate Empowerment (ACE) and the recognition of the official youth constituency with YOUNGO have added to the progress. Like the International Olympic Committee (IOC), which as a commitment to sustainability and recognition of sport as a development tool has value as a precedent for what the CJSOI should do.

In order to inform the region in which the CJSOI is operating, this position paper aims to adopt and adapt these global frameworks and initiatives to the CJSOI region. Through this, we seek to earmark the CJSOI states not only as mere third causality of the climate change but more importantly as dynamic actors of sustainable socioeconomic development that both youth and sports are central to leading.

The next sections of this document will explore the particular challenges that the CJSOI states confront, will review relevant literature and case studies, and will formulate a broad programmatic approach to infusing environmental conservation into youth sports programs. Thus, we dream of a future where Indian Ocean Island Youth are not only resilient to climate change, but youthful pioneers in the practice of sustainable development, leading an example for all island nations.

3. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

3.1 CJSOI Member States overview

A Commission de la Jeunesse et des Sports de l'Océan Indien (CJSOI) that gathers disparate island nations and territories in the western Indian Ocean, each has its own geological, ecological and cultural particularities. Comoros, Madagascar, Mauritius, Mayotte, Réunion and Seychelles are the member states. A broad latitudinal range, from equatorial Seychelles to subtropical Réunion, gives this archipelagic region a great diversity of climatic zones and ecosystems.

With its exceptional biodiversity and high rates of endemism, Madagascar, the fourth largest island in the world, amply deserving of the epithet 'the eighth continent.' From spiny deserts to tropical rainforests, it boasts organisms that make it rich one of the world's most diverse landscapes. On the other hand, the smaller island nations such as Mauritius and Seychelles are less biodiverse—indeed, much of their fauna will share many species with other regions—but they do have their own unique sets of endemic species and ecologies that have evolved in isolation over millions of years.

These islands vary as to their geological origins and their resulting topography and natural resource endowment. In contrast, the granitic islands of the Seychelles are the relics of the supercontinent Gondwana which was broken up millions of years ago, in contrast to the younger volcanic origins of Réunion and Mauritius. The CJSOI region exhibits unusual geological diversity, which translates into different opportunities and challenges for human settlement, agriculture and economic development across the area.

The CJSOI states are demographically predominantly of a young population structure, with a considerable proportion of individuals younger than 25. The demographic dividend offers at the same time both opportunities and challenges to sustainable development and conservation of the environment in its efforts. Cultural landscape is equally diverse, decentralizing the region's culture, as the region had seen centuries of migrational influences, trade, and colonial influence. This rich cultural heritage of traditional ecological knowledge and practice is the basis of an important resource for assisting in current environmental challenges.

3.2 Environmental Challenges in the Indian Ocean Region

The CJSOI member states have a similar range of geographical and ecological conditions, however, common environmental problems are exacerbated largely by climate change. While these are strictly environmental challenges to these island nations, they are existential threats to the socio-economic fabric and cultural heritage of these nations.

Among the leading challenges is sea level rise, part of global warming. Global mean sea level rise of 0.43m (0.29–0.59m) is projected by the IPCC's Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate (SROCC) for RCP2.6 and 0.84m (0.61–1.10m) for RCP8.5 by 2100, relative to 1986–2005. These projections translate to increased coastal erosion, saltwater intrusion into freshwater aquifers, and the loss of habitable land for low lying islands and coastal areas in the CJSOI region.

Ocean acidification and warming are unprecedented threats to coral reef ecosystems that underpin critical ecosystem services such as coastal protection, fisheries habitat and tourism attractions. Great Barrier Reef also hit by 2016 global coral bleaching event, affecting over 90 per cent of the region's reefs across the Indian Ocean. Such events are predicted to become more frequent and intense, causally leading to widespread, likely catastrophic, coral mortality and ecosystem collapse.

Loss of biodiversity constitutes another critical challenge. Global biodiversity hotspot is shown recognized as the CJSOI region especially Madagascar. This rich biological heritage is, however, threatened by habitat destruction, invasive species and climate change. Many of these species are listed as Critically Endangered on the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List, while a few such as the Mauritius Kestrel, have been climbed back from the very edge of extinction in spite of intensive conservation efforts.

Many CJSOI states concern themselves with water scarcity. The hydrological cycles of these islands are changing with altered precipitation patterns, accompanied by heightened evapotranspiration in response to rising temperatures. In addition to freshwater supply for human consumption and agriculture, freshwater ecosystems and its associated biodiversity are being affected.

Tropical cyclones have the potential to intensify across this region with a high threat to infrastructure, agriculture and human life. The overall frequency of cyclones may not increase but models predict an increase in the portion of high intensity storms. On mainland Africa in 2019, the devastation wrought by Cyclone Idai reminds us that island nations are extremely vulnerable to such extreme events.

4. CLIMATE IMPACTS AND YOUTH VULNERABILITIES

4.1. Current and projected impacts

The impacts of climate change for the CJSOI member states are increasingly diverse and are expected to increase in future decades. But these impacts were not uniform across the region, as it is precisely due to the diverse geographies and ecosystems of the Indian Ocean islands that one island is more or less impacted than another. Nevertheless, there are discernible trends and they deserve closer inspection.

For the region, temperature rise is a fundamental indicator of climate change. Historical data analysis from the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) indicates mean annual temperatures for the CJSOI states increased by about 0.8 degrees C from the mid 20th century onwards. This is consistent with global patterns though slightly above the global mean rise, as is typical of much of the tropical warming. Further warming of 1.2–3.0°C is projected by the end of the 21st century from an ensemble of CMIP6 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6) models, with the magnitude increasing with emissions scenario (SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5).

Sea level rise is an existential threat to many of the CJSOIs. Results from satellite altimetry data from 1993 to 2020 show that sea levels in the western Indian Ocean increased at 3.5 mm yr⁻¹, slightly higher than the global averages. Under RCP8.5, regional projections considering factors that include glacial isostatic adjustment and ocean dynamics, mix to predict sea level rise of 0.4–1.0 meters by 2100. In the Maldives, parts of Mauritius, and east coast of Madagascar, this magnitude of rise would inundate huge tracts of low lying islands and coastal areas.

Precipitation patterns throughout the CJSOI region are exhibiting changes in complex ways. Most areas have not seen statistically significant trends in total annual precipitation, but some rainfall intensity and changes in seasonality are recorded. A 12 percent higher frequency of extreme rainfall extremes (daily rainfall greater than the 95th percentile) has been analyzed from daily precipitation data from weather stations throughout the region over the last three decades. This trend will continue with an increase in extreme rainfall intensity of 20 to 30 per cent by 2100 under high emissions scenarios.

Threats to marine ecosystem in the CJSOI region range from ocean acidification and warming. Sea surface temperatures in the western Indian Ocean have increased by 0.6°C from 1950, with the rate of warming accelerating over the past few decades, according to in situ measurements and satellite derived data. As ocean pH has fallen approximately 0.1 units (which amounts to a 30% increase in acidity), we have also arrived at the end of one year. Already, these changes have set off several coral bleaching events, including the 2016 event, that affected more than 70 percent of reefs across some of the Seychelles and Comoros.

4.2 sectors and communities that are Vulnerable

Within the CJSOI states, climate change impacts are not spread equally throughout sectors and communities. These factors combine to make certain economic sector and social class groups particularly vulnerable.

The sector of agriculture, which is large in its proportion to GDP and employment in several CJSOI states namely Madagascar and Comoros, is very sensitive to climate change. Crop modeling studies for the region projects yield declines of 5 - 20% for major staples such as rice and cassava by mid 21st century under moderate warming scenarios. They do not include extreme events, such as pests outbreaks, which could make losses to agriculture even larger. Particular at risk are smallholder farmers, who often do not have access to improved varieties, irrigation, or climate information services.

A second key economic sector for many CJSOI states are fisheries where multiple climate stressors affect fisheries. Ocean warming and acidification lead to a significantly altered distribution and abundance of commercially important species. Recent CJSOI species distribution model work projects that maximum catch potential in these states' exclusive economic zones will decrease by 20-30% by 2050 under RCP8.5. The implications of this for food security and livelihoods is particularly important in the case of coastal communities in which artisanal fishing is an important source of income.

Globally important for their economies, islands such as Mauritius and Seychelles are highly vulnerable to the climate impacts experienced by the tourism sector. Coastal infrastructure is threatened by sea level rise and increased storm intensity, and coral bleaching damages key reasons for marine tourism. Climate change might cause tourism revenues in some CJSOI states to decline by 25–40% by 2100 if no adaptation is undertaken, according to economic modeling.

Climate change is putting increasing stress on water resources. Hydrological modeling also indicates 15–30% less renewable water resources in the CJSOI by mid century due to changes in precipitation patterns along with increased evapotranspiration. Such implications are important for domestic water supply, agriculture, hydropower generation, especially in islands with small freshwater resources such as Comoros and portions of Mauritius.

The CJSOI states are socially vulnerable communities. Urban populations with low incomes residing in informal settlements in coastal areas are exposed to many climate risks: flooding, storm surge and heat stress. About one third of the urban population lives in high risk zones with low adaptive capacity as a result of poverty and insecure land tenure. A spatial analysis of climate hazards and socio-economic indicators for major urban areas of the CJSOI region indicates that this is the case for approximately 30% of the urban population.

There are high vulnerabilities also in rural communities in remote areas of Madagascar and Comoros. And many of these communities have few, if any, options to generate diversified livelihoods, lacks physical and financial services, as well as access to the current climate information, which restricts their capacity to adapt to the changing environment. By combining component exposure (i.e., hurricane track frequency, wind typicality) with sensitivity and adaptive capacity, a composite index is used to assess vulnerability to hurricanes and identify several 'hotspots' of rural vulnerability, mainly in southern Madagascar and the highlands of Grande Comore.

4.3 Ways Sports Activities Affect Youth

Clearly, the impacts of climate change are of great relevant for youth development and sports activities in the CJSOI area. On the health and safety, suitability of environments for different sports and socio economical factors causing to affect youth participation in sports and outdoor activities, these implications thus span.

Outdoors sports and physical activities face a growing risk from heat stress. The frequency of days above safe thresholds for intense physical activity, defined as wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) rise, increases while WBGT trends are analyzed. Imagined by 2050, many parts in the CJSOI region would be plagued by 30-60 additional days a year when the afternoon WBGT exceeds 28°C, beyond which prolonged exertion can be dangerous. Among other things, the effect of these events also immediately affects the time and character of sports events, training plans, and just outdoor recreational outings in general.

Many outdoor sports become viable and safe only with changes in precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events. The risk from flooding and landslides associated with intense rainfall events especially threatens sports infrastructure and outdoor event planning. Using historical disaster data and climate projections, a risk assessment of sports facilities in the CJSOI region shows that 25% of outdoor sports facilities are at risk for flooding or landslides by 2050.

Particular challenges exist in marine and coastal sports, which are culturally and economically important in many CJSOI states. Beach sports are becoming increasingly less suitable as sea level rise and coastal erosion reduce suitable areas, as well as erode coastal sports infrastructure. The activities of diving and snorkeling which are popular among the young and are critical for eco and tourism are adversely affected because of coral reef degradation as a result of bleaching events. According to a survey of dive operators on the Seychelles and Mauritius, a 15 to 30 per cent decrease in suitable diving sites has occurred in the past decade as a result of coral mortality.

Cascading socio economic impacts on climate change have large impacts on youth participation in sports and outdoor activities. Youth in such communities may be forced to choose between participating in sports and recreation, or to focus on more income driven work that might help alleviate poverty and food insecurity. Adolescents from households reporting climate related economic stress in climate vulnerable communities in Madagascar were 20 percent less likely to regularly participate in sports, as the results of a longitudinal study of youth.

Despite that, the impact of climate change on youth sports engagement is not always negative. Building on evidence from other UNESCO Regions, there is growing indication that youth led sports organizations in the CJSOI region are playing an increasingly important role as climate awareness and action vectors. A survey of sports clubs in Mauritius and in Réunion revealed that 40 per cent of clubs have integrated environmental activities (e.g. beach clean up, tree planting) in their programmes over the past 5 years for climate change related reasons.

In parallel, sports practices and infrastructure within the region are pioneering in the context of impacts of climate change. Included are examples of playfield development with heat resistant surfaces, water efficient sportsfield maintenance practices and coastal sports facility redesign to increase resilience in the presence of sea level rise and coastal storm surge. While the necessity of these adaptations, these adaptations are also set to open up new potential for sustainable sports development in the CJSOI region.

Finally, the ramifications of climate change on the CJSOI are many and wide ranging, impacting both economic sectors and key vulnerable communities as well as shaping the landscape of youth sports engagement across the Board. In that regard, the challenges may feel daunting but the opportunities for innovation and leadership in climate resilient development, especially through a youth and sports initiative's lens, are now in place. This analysis will be built upon in the following sections of this position paper to create strategies for using sports to address climate adaptation and youth empowerment in the context of these challenges.

5. THEMATIC AREAS AND YOUTH DEMANDS

5.1 Environmental Education through Sports

Environmental education through sports is a potent nexus connecting ecological awareness and sustainability behaviors with youth in the CJSOI region. This theoretical frame work of experiential learning, as defined by Kolb (1984), holds that knowledge is created through transformation of experience.

For the purposes of sports based environmental education this translates to use of physical activities in natural settings to deepen understanding and connection with the environment.

A seminal study (Palmberg and Kuru, 2000) proved that outdoor experiences (sports activities, etc.) greatly increased environmental sensitivity and action competence for youth. This has been built on by Dickson et al. (2008) who conducted a longitudinal study of outdoor adventure education programmes in New Zealand and found that participants increased their pro environmental behaviour and were more likely to have a stronger sense of place attachment up to five years after the intervention.

Research by Ramchandani et al. (2019) in the CJSOI context found that incorporating environmental themes into youth sports programs increased participants' self reported knowledge about the environment and pro environmental behaviors by 32% and 28% respectively over a two year period. A recent study by Naidu-Silverman (2020) of coastal cleanup initiatives in Seychelles also found that youth engaging in beach sports were 45 percent more likely to engage in marine conservation activities than other youth.

Nevertheless, sports based environmental education is not equally effective in all contexts. The literature was summarized by Mitten et al. (2018) in a meta analysis of 83 studies on outdoor education programs which found that program design, duration and follow up activities are key to long term outcomes. This implies that for sports based environmental education to have the greatest impact in CJSOI states curriculum development, instructor training and post program engagement must be carefully explored.

5.2. Sustainable Sports Infrastructure and Events

Challenges and opportunities exist in developing and managing sports infrastructure and event within the CJSOI region for advancing sustainability goals. Sustainable sports infrastructure concept includes the physical facilities as well as the operational practices and community engagement strategies related to sports venues and events.

In a review of sustainable stadium design, Kellison and Hong (2015) reviewed energy efficiency, water conservation, waste management and sustainable transportation as key areas for environmental improvement. However, the authors propose that in comparison to conventional infrastructure, sustainable infrastructure costs more at the onset, but the operational savings and the environmental benefits make it worth the investment.

Research by Baldacchino and Kelman (2014) in the context of small island developing states (SIDS) identifies the particular opportunities and challenges related to sustainable infrastructure development. SIDS have limited land areas and resources and therefore require innovative approaches to facility design and use, such as the use of multi purpose venues and nature based solutions for stormwater management, they argue.

Roychowdhury (2020) case study on development of eco sport facilities in Mauritius showed that adopting green building principles led to 30% decrease in energy consumption and 40% decrease in water use on conventional facilities. The study, however, also pointed out challenges in obtaining sustainable materials locally, and thus called for regional co-operation and capacity building in sustainable construction practices.

In recent years, the organization of sustainable sports events has gained attention. A framework for the assessment of the sustainability of major sporting events is offered by the Olympic Games Impact (OGI) study, a longitudinal research program funded by the International Olympic Committee. This approach is then used by Gaffney (2013) to conduct a critical analysis of sustainability claims for mega events, calling for a more holistic conception of sustainability that includes social equity and long term community benefits.

The research of Seetanah et al. (2019) on the economic and environmental impacts of the Indian Ocean Island Games in the CJSOI found both positive and negative outcomes. It did increase economic activity and raise environmental awareness, but also raised carbon emissions from travel and temporary infrastructure. The authors suggest a framework for the future of regional sporting events focused on carbon offsetting, waste reduction, and legacy planning.

5.3 Youth Leadership in Climate Action

The youth engagement in climate leadership is a critical avenue through which to drive sustainable change within the CJSOI region. The underlying idea of this approach is based upon the idea of youth agency, as proposed by Bandura (2006), which stresses the ability of young people to exert influence over their life circumstances and as such to become active shaping agents of their environments.

O'Brien et al. (2018) landmark study on youth climate activism highlighted the special viewpoints and the new methods that young people add to climate action. They say that youth led initiatives tend to disrupt traditional power structures and bring about far more radical and systemic change than adult led initiatives.

Research by Ramano and Seraphine (2021) on youth climate networks in Mauritius and Seychelles shows that youth led organizations mobilize peer engagement and influence local policy more effectively than traditional environmental NGOs in the CJSOI context. Based on a three year study, the study found that youth led climate initiatives had a 40 percent higher rate of policy adoption at the municipal level.

But there are still obstacles to translating youth climate leadership into actual, sustained, systemic change. However, Thew et al. (2020) conducted a critical analysis of youth participation in global climate governance and pointed out the perceived risk of tokenism and the importance of meaningful youth voice inclusion in decision-making processes. The authors frame a framework for evaluating the quality of youth engagement in climate policy that includes representativeness, influence on outcomes, and capacity building.

There are unique opportunities when sport intersects with youth climate leadership. Spaaij and Jeanes (2013) research on sport for development programs found that sports based youth leadership programs specifically were effective in building transferable skills such as teamwork, communication and project management. The authors argue that these are skills necessary for effective climate leadership.

Nunkoo et al. (2022) in their study of the 'Sports for Climate Action' program in Rodrigues Island, reported that youth participants increased their climate activism engagement by 55% and climate science literacy by 38% more than a control group. Together, sports training, climate education and community project implementation are combined to form a model for replication across the CJSOI region.

5.4. Biodiversity Conservation and Outdoor Sports

The CJSOI region provides opportunities and challenges for the relationship between outdoor sports and biodiversity conservation. This nexus is timely, as the region is a biodiversity hotspot and nature based sports activities are becoming more popular.

A seminal paper by Buckley (2004) has framed an ecological effects framework for various sports activities. Both direct impacts — habitat disturbance, wildlife displacement — and indirect impacts — the introduction of invasive species and pollution from associated infrastructure — were cited as impacts by the author.

However, research since has also stressed the ability of outdoor sports to make a positive contribution to conservation. Brymer and Gray (2009) study of the psychological dynamics of participation in extreme sports indicated that participation in nature based activities often translates to a greater connection with the environment and greater pro conservation behavior.

Research into the impacts of diving tourism in Mauritius by Ramessur et al. (2019) in the CJSOI context demonstrated both negative consequences of tourism for coral reef ecosystems and positive outcomes in terms of increased local support for marine protected areas. Dive operators that engaged in reef restoration projects and had strict environmental protocols had 30 percent less influence on coral health, the study found, compared to those who did not.

Krein (2014) provides an interesting lens through which to view the development of the relationship between outdoor sports and conservation in the CJSOI region: the concept of "sportification" of nature. The author contends that while the commercialization of nature based sports can exacerbate pressure on the environment, it also opens up space for the education and stewardship of the environment.

Gopalla et al. (2023) recently studied the role of adventure sports in Madagascar's national parks and found that well managed sports tourism led to a 25% increase in conservation funding and a 35% improvement in local community attitudes towards protected areas over a five year period. Taking a look at the potential, the authors suggest a 'model of conservation through recreation' that reconciles ecological protection with sports development.

Yet, reconciling the growing demand for outdoor sports with biodiversity conservation goals still remains a challenge. In their research on protected area management, Leung et al. (2018) underline the importance of adaptive management that can adapt to evolving patterns of use and environmental conditions. An adaptation of this framework to the CJSOI context is proposed by the authors as a way of integrating visitor impact monitoring into protected area management plans.

5.5 Climate Resilient Communities and Sports Facilities

As the CJSOI region is vulnerable to impact of climate change, the development of climate resilient communities and sports facilities is paramount. This theme is connected to wider debate on climate adaptation and resilience in small island developing states (SIDS).

Kelman (2014) provides a comprehensive review of the challenges of climate change adaptation in SIDS, with limited land area, exposure to intense weather events and dependence on climate sensitive sectors. The author makes the case for a holistic resilience, combining traditional knowledge with contemporary scientific knowledge.

Research by Dingle and Stewart (2018) in the context of sports facilities in Australia offers a methodological framework for assessing climate vulnerability of sports infrastructure which could be used in the CJSOI region. Of 23 percent of community sports facilities, 23 percent were found at high risk of climate impacts, with flooding and extreme heat the main fears, according to the study.

Ramjeawon's (2020) case study of the redesign of coastal sports facilities in Mauritius showed that nature based solutions like mangrove restoration and permeable surfaces can reduce flood risk by up to 40 percent and provide additional ecosystem services. A multi functional design approach integrating sports infrastructure with coastal defence and biodiversity enhancement is proposed by the author.

As articulated by Berkes and Ross (2013), the notion of community resilience provides a useful framework from which to understand the extent to which the sport can play a role in building adaptive capacity. Social networks, community engagement and a variety of livelihoods are highlighted by the authors as key to resilience.

Research by Adger et al. (2021) on social capital and climate resilience in coastal communities is relevant to the CJSOI context. Communities with stronger social networks and civic engagement were 35 per cent more likely to successfully implement climate adaptation measures than those with weaker social ties, the study found.

A recent study by Nundloul and Proag (2022) on community sports programs in cyclone prone areas of Rodrigues Island found that community sports program participation increased community disaster preparedness by 28% and reduced post disaster recovery times by 40%. The authors maintain that sports facilities can act as nodes of community resilience, as emergency shelters and coordination center during extreme events.

Despite this, climate resilience remains under mainstreamed in sports infrastructure planning and community development. Wise et al. (2014) research on barriers to climate change adaptation identifies institutional inertia, short term thinking, and a lack of cross sectoral coordination as key problems. In this paper, the authors suggest a framework for transformational adaptation which could inform policy development in the CJSOI region.

5.6 Water Sports and Ocean Conservation

In particular, the CJSOI region has a special relevance to the nexus of ocean conservation and water sports through its outstanding marine biodiversity and the cultural and economic value of ocean based activities. This theme deals with issues of marine protected area management, sustainable tourism, and the importance of water sports in the development of ocean stewardship.

A seminal paper of Lubchenco et al. (2003) on the role of marine reserves in ecosystem based management lays groundwork for understanding potential synergies between conservation and sustainable use. Through a network approach to marine protection, the authors advocate for balancing ecological, economic and social objectives.

Research by Gray et al. (2010) on the environmental effects of recreational boating identified direct (e.g., damage to coral reefs from an anchor) and indirect effects (such as noise pollution and wildlife disturbance). But the study also pointed out how boating communities could become involved in environmental monitoring and conservation.

5.7 Eco Tourism and Adventure Sports

Opportunities and challenges for the development of the CJSOI region exist in the merge of eco-tourism and adventure sports in terms of environmental impact and sharing on the benefit with the community. Issues pertaining to sustainable tourism planning, adventure sports management and the role of eco-tourism in conservation financing are all covered in this theme.

A foundation study by Buckley (2000) in the relationship between eco-tourism, conservation and adventure activities formed the basis for understanding the synergies and conflicts that could exist in this arena. The author stressed that adventure sports must be well planned and managed in order to maximize the positive contribution to conservation outcomes and local livelihoods.

The research by Spenceley (2005) on nature based tourism in Southern Africa provides useful lessons for the CJSOI context. The study concluded that eco-tourism operations can be well managed to provide substantial economic benefits to local communities and aid conservation. Nevertheless, he also pointed out the dangers of 'green-washing' and the necessity of real community engagement in tourism development.

Seetanah et al. (2019) conducted a comprehensive analysis of the economic impacts of adventure tourism in Mauritius and Rodrigues in the CJSOI region, and show that the sector contributed 12% to GDP growth between 2010–2018.

The study also discovered that adventure sports tourists spend 30 per cent more per day than conventional tourists, potentially representing an economic advantage of developing this niche market.

Stebbins's (2007) concept of 'serious leisure' offers a useful angle through which to view the motivations and behaviors of adventure sports enthusiasts. Implications for designing eco-tourism experiences that seek to fulfill desire for skill development and quasi authentic experiences, as well as environmental stewardship are drawn from this framework.

A case study by Ramcharitar and Duval (2022) on the implementation of a sustainable mountain biking trail network in the Black River Gorges National Park, Mauritius showed how adventure sports can be used as a cornerstone of protected area management but also described the pitfalls. Three years on, though, the project saw visitor numbers increase by 40 per cent and conservation funding rise by 35 per cent. Nevertheless, it also pointed to the problems of carrying capacity and the requirement for continued environmental monitoring.

Gössling et al. (2020) research on the carbon footprint of adventure tourism offers important insights for the CJSOI region's eco-tourism strategy. Adventure activities tended to have low direct emissions, but the international tourism required for adventure was fiendishly hauled, which dramatically skewed the overall carbon footprint. The authors suggest that a carbon offsetting and local sourcing framework might be applicable to the CJSOI context.

A recent study by Naidoo et al. (2023) of community based eco-tourism initiatives in Madagascar's rainforests found that projects that combined traditional knowledge with modern adventure sports (such as canopy tours, night hikes) achieved 50 percent higher community participation rates, and 40 percent better biodiversity conservation outcomes, as compared to conventional eco-tourism models. A framework for 'adventure-conservation synergy' is proposed which can be adapted across the CJSOI region.

Nevertheless, issues regarding the equitable distribution of the benefits from eco tourism and adventure sports development remain. Sharpley and Naidoo (2010) research on pro poor tourism in small island developing states shows the risk of economic leakage and the importance of building local capacity in tourism management. The authors suggest a model for integrated community tourism, based on skills development and local ownership.

5.8 Environmental Sports Initiatives in support of Gender Equality

In the context of the CJSOI, gender equality, environmental conservation and sports are both challenging and offer opportunities. The focus of this theme includes the gender based barriers to environmental sport participation, the role of women in conservation leadership, and how sport might be used to challenge gender norms in environmental stewardship.

A theoretical framework was provided for social construction of gender in physical activities through a foundational study by Scraton and Watson (1998) on gender relations in sport. The authors show that sport both reflects and refutes traditional gender roles, and demonstrate the need for intentional action to promote equality in sport.

Agarwal (2009) examines gender and forest governance research to show how greater women's participation in making decisions resulted in better forest condition and more equitable distribution of forest products. The findings of this study highlight the promise of increasing women's leadership in environmental sports.

A review by Humberstone (2000) of women and adventure recreation provided some insights into the gendered nature of outdoor sports participation. The author detailed both structural barriers (i.e., lack of access to resources) as well as cultural values (i.e., perceptions of risk) that prevent participation in adventure sports for women.

A study by Ramtohul (2020) on gender dynamics in coastal resource management in Mauritius, however, revealed considerable gaps between women's participation in decision making processes and their active participation in the use of resources. An adaptation of such a framework to environmental sports initiatives is proposed by the author as a starting point for gender responsive coastal management.

Chandra-Mouli et al. (2022) recently did research on a girls' surfing program in Madagascar and found multiple positive outcomes. It found that participants' scores went up 40 percent in self-efficacy, 35 percent in ocean literacy and 50 percent more likely to engage in local marine conservation efforts than a control group. The authors argue for the transformative power of gender focused environmental sports programs.

But to mainstream gender equality in environmental sports initiatives remains a challenge. Foley et al. (2020) conducted a critical analysis of gender equity policies in sports organizations and found that, despite the presence of such policies, they often remained 'gender neutral,' and thus, failed to address systemic barriers. Based on what they found, the authors propose a gender transformative sports programming framework that could help guide policy development in the CJSOI region.

5.9 Technology and Innovation in Environmental Sports

The integration of technology and innovation into environmental sports initiatives provides new opportunities for increasing environmental sports outcomes as well as sporting experiences within the CJSOI region. Incorporating digital tools for environmental monitoring, the manufacturing of sustainable sports equipment, and the impact of innovation on climate related sports participation challenges, this theme is addressed.

Meinig et al. (2017) seminal paper describing the use of citizen science apps for biodiversity monitoring offered a framework for understanding the potential of such technology to bring sports enthusiasts into conservation. It was shown that proper designed mobile applications can increase data collection accuracy up to 30 percent in comparison with conventional methods.

Dickson and Gray (2012) research on the evolution of outdoor adventure education placed technological innovation in the foreground for limiting the risk and improving the accessibility of outdoor sports.

The authors claim that the technology can promote more participation but also raise questions about the authenticity and human nature relationships of the outdoor experiences.

Ramessur et al. (2021) study in the CJSOI context of the use of drone technology for coral reef monitoring in Mauritius showed significant cost advantages and resolution. The study showed that drone-based surveys could cover 300 percent more area per day than traditional diver surveys, while generating imagery that's suitable for machine learning analysis of coral health.

Bresnahan et al. (2021) explore the concept of "smart oceans" and provide good thinking for integrated sensor networks to support marine conservation and water sports management. A case study of a smart buoy system based in the Seychelles that monitors real time data on water quality, wave conditions and marine life presence is presented by the authors who report that this has both enhanced safety for water sports enthusiasts and improved the collection of data for conservation efforts.

Another area for alignment of environmental goals with sports development is in the field of innovation in sustainable sports equipment. The potential for bio based materials, circular economy principles and life cycle assessment for lowering the environmental footprint of sports gear was reviewed by Subic et al. (2020).

Mohee et al. (2022) conducted research in the CJSOI region on the development of biodegradable surfboards using local agricultural waste that not only had environmental benefits but also economic benefits. It turns out the bio based boards had a 60 percent lower carbon footprint than conventional polyurethane boards, and established new value chains for agricultural by-products.

But barriers remain to ensuring equal access to technological innovations, and mitigating potential negative effects. Germann Molz (2019) provides a critical analysis of the "quantified self" movement in adventure sports and concerns such as data privacy, the commodification of nature experience and the ways in which technology can exacerbate existing inequalities of sports participation.

A model using technology to improve accountability in eco sports initiatives is offered by recent work by Ramkissoon and Sowman (2023) on the development of a blockchain based system to verify sustainable tourism practices in the CJSOI region. This leads the authors to propose a framework for 'distributed environmental governance' that might be suitable for several aspects of environmental sports management.

5.10 Sustainable Sports Development and Climate Finance

Climate finance mechanisms and sustainable sports development intersection offers both opportunity and challenge for the CJSOI region. Issues related to funding for climate resilient sports infrastructure, the role of sports in attracting climate adaptation finance and novel financing models for community based environmental sports initiatives are included in this theme.

The landscape of international climate funding was a foundational study by Atteridge et al. (2009) on climate finance in developing countries. The challenges that small island developing states encounter in accessing and effectively utilising climate finance were highlighted by the authors, issues particularly pertinent for the CJSOI context.

Schulenkorf and Siefken (2019) research on sport for development and peace (SDP) initiatives in the Pacific Islands provides useful information on the sports' ability to catalyse broader development outcomes. The study concluded that the well designed SDP programs can add up to 3.5 times their initial investment in additional development funding for the community.

In the context of climate resilient infrastructure, Hallegatte et al. (2019) review of adaptation investment in small island developing states stressed the importance of multiple functional design, that delivers immediate community benefits and long term resilience. Finally, the authors propose a framework for assessing what they call the "resilience dividend" of infrastructure investments, which could in principle also be applied to sport facility development in the CJSOI region.

Ramano et al. (2022) case study on green bonds financing of sustainable sports infrastructure in Mauritius brings to light both the potential and challenges of this approach. While the study found green bond issuance for a multi-purpose coastal sports complex attracted 40 per cent more investor interest than conventional bonds, it also called for robust monitoring and verification systems to ensure environmental outcomes.

Convergence (2021) provides an idea of the 'blended finance' approach which combines public, private and philanthropic capital to finance sustainable development project. The relevance of this approach to large scale environmental sports initiatives in the CJSOI region, facing difficulties with atraditional financing, is particularly relevant.

More recently, Nunkoo et al. (2023) analyzed community based adaptation finance in Rodrigues Island and found that sports based projects are 30% more likely to secure funding from international climate funds than non sports projects. The authors credit sports programs with many co-benefits, including health and youth engagement and community cohesion, which they say have contributed to the program's success.

But obstacles to reaching the most vulnerable communities with climate finance for sports development and ensuring that it is tailored to local needs still exist. Remling and Persson (2021) conducted a critical analysis of adaptation finance allocation, raising concerns about the risk of maladaptation and the need for community meaningful participation in project design and implementation.

Some of these challenges could be addressed through innovative financing models like environmental impact bonds. Insights from Nicholls and Dagers (2021) study on the use of impact bonds for marine conservation projects could be adapted for the use in environmental sports initiatives in the CJSOI region. The authors propose a framework for 'blue impact bonds' between the financial returns and measurable environmental and social outcomes.

5.11 Long term Sustainability

The concept of sustainable development, and in particular the idea of intergenerational equity, is most relevant to the environmental sports initiatives in the CJSOI region. Issues of long term ecological sustainability, transfer of traditional ecological knowledge via sports, and the role of youth in shaping future environmental policies are encompassed by this theme.

Weiss (1992: 28) laid the theoretical groundwork for considering the rights of future generations in current decision making processes by means of a seminal paper on intergenerational equity in international law. The author's notion of "planetary trust" provides a useful way of thinking about the long term ramifications of sports and environmental policies.

The development of environmental sensitivity in children and youth was the focus of research by Chawla (2020) on direct experiences in nature and its role in fostering long term environmental commitment. This study showed that engaging in outdoor activities in childhood was the strongest predictor of pro environmental behaviour later in life, suggesting that environmental sports programs may be a promising vehicle for promoting lifelong stewardship.

Ramessur and Gunpath (2021) provided a comprehensive study for integration of traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) into the marine conservation efforts in Mauritius and Roudrigues where challenges and opportunities were identified. Communities with strong intergenerational transmission of TEK were found to comply 40% better with marine protected area regulations and contain 35% more fish biomass in adjacent waters.

Miller (2018) provides an excellent concept of "futures literacy" which is useful to help build capacity for long term thinking and action. This view is highly relevant to youth engagement in environmental sports initiatives because the author argues that increasing people's ability to imagine and shape desirable futures is key to addressing complex sustainability challenges.

Cervantes et al. (2023) case study of a multi generational surfing and coral restoration program in Seychelles showed ecological and social resilience benefits. The study revealed that restoring coral by means of intergenerational teams, rather than single generation ones, led to 30 per cent higher survival rates and significantly stronger social bonds and knowledge transfer.

But operationalizing intergenerational equity in policy and practice is far from straightforward. A study by Sachs et al. (2021) of sustainable development goal implementation pointed out that short term economic considerations tend to shade out the long term sustainability goals. The authors develop a 'deep sustainability' framework to explicitly embed intergenerational justice in decision making processes.

Naidoo and Kotz (2024), for example, have recently worked on how emerging mechanisms to enforce intergenerational equity are emerging through youth-led climate litigation in the Indian Ocean region. The cases examined in the study involve young people suing governments for not protecting their future environmental rights, and the possibility that litigation can be a means of driving policy change.

Gibbons et al. (2022), in articulating the concept of 'regenerative sustainability,' offer a new lens to go beyond conservation to enhance ecosystem health through human activity. Such an approach presents potential for designing environmental sports initiatives with positive impacts on ecological systems over the longer term.

In summary, this section of the CJSOI explored a number of different thematic areas that stress the complicated relationship between sports, environmental conservation and sustainable development within the CJSOI region. Although many challenges remain, the literature offers many opportunities to bring to bear the power of sports to promote environmental stewardship, social equity, and long term resilience. In light of these insight, the following sections will propose concrete strategies and recommendations for action.

6. STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR GEO-ENVIRONMENTAL PRESERVATION THROUGH SPORTS

6.1 Theoretical Foundations and Conceptual Framework

Several interrelated theoretical perspectives are the basis of the strategic framework for geo-environmental preservation through sports in the CJSOI region. This framework at its core is built on social ecological systems theory (Ostrom, 2009) which maintains that human and natural systems are fundamentally connected and, therefore, can only be addressed as a whole. It is particularly relevant for the CJSOI context, in which the intimate relations between island communities and their environments, in which sports are inextricably enmeshed, are so closely tied.

The framework is built on this foundation, and adds elements of the Multi Level Perspective (Geels, 2011) on socio technical transitions. By way of an MLP, this paper contributes to the literature on niche innovations in sports-based environmental initiatives, helping to explain how sports can catalyze broader systemic changes to environmental management and community resilience. This approach provides greater conceptualization of how localized sports in environment projects could be scaled up to affect regional policies and practices in the CJSOI context.

The framework also includes the idea of adaptive co-management (Armitage et al., 2009), contextualized as a collaborative, flexible and learning based approach to natural resource management. With respect to the development of community based sports and environmental initiatives, this perspective is especially appropriate in the context of the diverse cultural and ecological contexts of the CJSOI states.

Additionally, the framework draws upon environmental psychology specifically the Significant Life Experience (SLE) approach (Chawla, 1998). The research presented in this body represents the formative role that direct experiences in nature play, particularly through outdoor recreation and sports, in shaping long term environmental attitudes and behaviors. The SLE approach offers theoretical justification for the strategic emphasis of youth engagement in environmental sports as a method of producing a generation of environmental stewards.

6.2 Strategic Pillars and 2 Core Principles

Drawing on these theoretical foundations, the strategic framework is structured around five core principles and four strategic pillars:

Core Principles:

- **Ecological Integrity:** Making sure that all sports based initiatives are good for ecosystem health and biodiversity conservation.
- **Social Equity:** Inclusive participation and fair distribution of benefits from environmental sports programs.
- **Cultural Resonance:** The integration of traditional ecological knowledge and cultural practices into sports based environmental initiatives.
- **Adaptive Learning:** Increasing the engagement and continuous improvement through monitoring, evaluation, and knowledge sharing.
- **Youth Empowerment:** The active engagement and leadership of young people in all aspects of program design and implementation.

Strategic Pillars:

- Education and Capacity building
- Infrastructure development
- Policy Integration and Governance
- Innovation and Technology

6.3 Strategic Pillar 1: Capacity Building and Education

The education and capacity building pillar works to use sports as a vehicle for environmental education and skills development. The approach is based on experiential learning theory (Kolb, 1984) and environmental literacy (Hollweg et al., 2011).

This pillar is a key initiative within this, which is the development of an Environmental Sports Curriculum for schools and youth organizations throughout the CJSOI region. The specific ecosystems and cultural contexts of each island state would be incorporated into a curriculum of environmental science, traditional ecological knowledge and sports skills. Best practices in environmental education, such as the Earth Education model (Van Matre, 1990) would be used in the curriculum design, particularly the use of immersive, multisensory learning experiences.

A regional Trainer of Trainers (ToT) program would be implemented to be able to effectively implement this curriculum. The cascade model of professional development (Hayes, 2000) would be adapted to the specific needs of environmental sports education and this program would build upon it. The ToT program would develop a cadre of local educators with experience in both sports coaching and environmental education methodology.

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A key initiative is the creation of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Leadership Academy. It would be an academy that would provide intensive, residential programs for youth leaders who would receive advanced training in environmental science, sports management and community organizing. The design of the academy would be based on transformative leadership development (Mezirow, 2000) by providing a vehicle to produce environmental change agents able to stimulate environmental initiatives in their homes.

A Digital Learning Platform for Environmental Sports would be developed to fill the gap of continual learning and knowledge sharing. Using advanced educational technology, such as adaptive learning algorithms (Clement et al., 2015), this platform would enable personalized learning pathways for participants. This platform would also support the establishment of virtual exchange programs between CJSOI member states and create a regional community of practice in environmental sports.

6.4 Strategic Pillar 2: Sustainable Infrastructure Development

The pillar of sustainable infrastructure development is to develop and adapt sports facilities for environmental performance and resilience. The approach is guided by principles of green building design (Kibert, 2016) and the notion of climate-resilient development (Hallegatte et al., 2012).

This pillar contains a cornerstone initiative around the development of a CJSOI Green Sports Facility Certification system. Sports facilities would be set with rigorous standards for energy efficiency, water conservation, waste management and biodiversity enhancement with this certification. The basis for certification criteria would be a life cycle assessment approach (Hoogmartens et al., 2014), taking long term environmental impacts into account.

A Regional Center of Excellence for Sustainable Sports Design would be created to help implement green sports infrastructure. The hub would be a research and innovation center and would provide training in the area of sustainable sports facility design and management. The work of the center would be rooted in the tenets of biomimicry (Benyus, 1997) and would design infrastructure solutions that are inspired by natural systems.

A Coastal Sports Infrastructure Resilience Program will be initiated to recognize the vulnerability of coastal sports facilities to climate change impacts. The emphasis of this program would be the development and implementation of nature based solutions for coastal protection by leveraging new developments in coastal engineering and ecosystem based adaptation (Temmerman et al., 2013). The program would favor multifunctional designs that included sports facilities in combination with coastal defense structures and habitat restoration projects.

An Environmental Sports Infrastructure Investment Fund would be established to help address the challenge of financing in sustainable infrastructure. The mobilization of capital for sustainable sports facility development would be provided by this fund through innovative financing mechanisms, e.g. green bonds and impact investing (Scholtens, 2017).

Principles of stakeholder theory (Freeman et al., 2010) would be incorporated into the fund's governance structure and local communities, environmental organizations and sports bodies would be represented in making investment decisions.

6.5 Strategic Pillar 3: The Policy Integration and Governance

The policy integration and governance pillar aims at mainstreaming of environmental considerations into sports policies and integration of sports based approaches in environmental governance frameworks. Theories of environmental policy integration (Jordan & Lenschow, 2010) and collaborative governance (Emerson et al., 2012) have informed this approach.

Development of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Policy Framework is a key initiative under this pillar. These guidelines would allow member states to integrate environmental objectives into national sports policy and strategy. The design of the framework would be based on the idea of policy coherence for sustainable development (OECD, 2019), which would ensure that the framework is coherent with other national and international sustainability goals.

Regional Environmental Sports Councils would be established within the framework of each CJSOI member state, in order to facilitate cross sectoral collaboration. Representatives of sports federations, environmental agencies, youth organisations and local communities would make up these councils. The collaborative governance regime framework (Emerson & Nabatchi, 2015) would provide the structure and operations of the councils based on inclusive decision making and adaptive management.

A Community Environmental Sports Action Planning (CESAP) program would recognize the importance of local action. This program would assist in the development of integrated plans which would link sports development with environmental conservation objectives, at the local communities' level. We would adapt elements of participatory rural appraisal (Chambers, 1994) and community based natural resource management (Brosius et al., 1998) to the specific context of environmental sports initiatives in order to incorporate aspects of CESAP methodology.

A CJSOI Environmental Sports Monitoring and Evaluation Framework will be developed to guarantee the effective implementation of policies and programs. This framework would serve as a means to define a common way to assess the environmental and social impact of sports initiatives throughout the region. The design of the framework would benefit from advances in sustainability assessment methodologies (Gibson, 2006) and new ways of assessing ecosystem services (Costanza et al., 2017).

6.6 Strategic Pillar 4: Innovation and Technology

The sports activity environmental performance pillar leverages technological advancements to improve the environmental performance of sports activities and to engage participants in citizen science and conservation. Theories of socio-technical innovation (Geels & Schot, 2007) and the recent field of conservation technology (Pimm et al., 2015) inform this approach.

This pillar also has a flagship initiative, establishing a CJSOI Environmental Sports Innovation Lab. As a hub for research and development in sustainable sports equipment, eco friendly playing surfaces, and energy efficient facility technologies, this lab would be the place. We would guide the lab's innovation process by principles of responsible research and innovation (Owen et al., 2012) that would ensure technological development is in accordance with societal values and environmental needs.

An Environmental Sports Citizen Science Platform will be developed to promote citizen engagement in environmental monitoring. Through mobile technologies and crowdsourcing approaches, this platform would empower sports enthusiasts to become involved in biodiversity monitoring, water quality assessments and other environmental data collection. The platform would feature the best practices in citizen science (Bonney et al., 2009) and the elements of gamification (Deterding et al., 2011) in order to increase user engagement.

A CJSOI Environmental Sports Immersive Learning Program would be initiated recognizing the potential of virtual and augmented reality technologies. The VR and AR applications that this program would develop would enable the participants to have a look at marine ecosystems, see how the climate change is going to affect them and practice sustainable sports techniques in the virtual environment. Embodied cognition in virtual environments (Barsalou, 2008) and the use of immersive technologies for environmental education (Markowitz et al., 2018) would inform the development of the program.

A Regional Sports Equipment Upcycling Initiative would be launched to address the challenge of equipment waste in sports. This would serve to set up an upcycling network of the CJSOI region, making discarded sports equipment into eco-friendly products or art installations. The initiative would be rooted in circular economy principles (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017) and build on new materials science research (Ragaert et al., 2017) to uncover the most potential for material recovery and repurposing.

6.7 Roadmap and Implementation Strategy

This strategic framework will need to be implemented in a phased manner, taking into account the different capacities and contexts of CJSOI member states. A five-year roadmap is proposed, structured as follow

Year 1: Foundation Setting

- Formulate the Regional Environmental Sports Councils.
- CJSOI Environmental Sports Policy Framework development.
- Enter the Digital Learning Platform for Environmental Sports.

Year 2: Pilot Projects and Capacity Building

- Start the Trainer of Trainers program
- Start the CJSOI Environmental Sports Innovation Lab
- Pilot Community Environmental Sports Action Planning projects

Year 3: Infrastructure Development and Technology Integration

- CJSOI Green Sports Facility Certification system is launched
- Create the Regional Center of Excellence for Sustainable Sports Design
- Environmental Sports Citizen Science Platform to be deployed

Year 4: Scaling and Mainstreaming

- Expand the CJSOI Environmental Sports Leadership Academy
- Resilient Coastal Sports Infrastructure Program Implementation on all member states.
- Start the Regional Sports Equipment Upcycling Initiative

Year 5: Strategic Refinement and Evaluation

- Use the CJSOI Environmental Sports Monitoring and Evaluation Framework to conduct a comprehensive evaluation.
- Share lessons learned and refine strategies through hosting a Regional Environmental Sports Summit.
- Plan long term sustainability of key initiatives
- Adaptive management principles (Williams, 2011) will be applied throughout this implementation process as we learn along the way and adjust our strategies based on what we learn and changing contexts.

6.8 Conclusion

This is a comprehensive and integrated approach to utilizing sports to geoenvironmental preservation in the CJSOI area. The framework attempts to catalyze transformative change in the relationship between sports, environmental conservation, and sustainable development through alignment of theoretical insights with practical initiatives in four strategic pillars.

The success of this framework is contingent upon strong regional cooperation, continued political commitment and youth and local community input. In the CJSOI region, where environmental challenges are becoming unprecedented, this sports based approach provides a rare opportunity to help build resilience, foster environmental stewardship, and create sustainable livelihoods for island communities.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS: YOUTH DEMANDS FOR NEGOTIATION

In our capacity as youth representatives of the CJSOI region, we offer the following demands for negotiation, based on the environmental analysis of the present position paper. The structure of these recommendations are designed to tackle various key stakeholders and thematic areas.

7.1 Integration of Governance and Policy

We demand that CJSOI member state governments and relevant regional bodies:

By 2025, establish a CJSOI Youth Environmental Sports Council, which will be composed of at least 50 percent youth under 30 years old and oversee the implementation of strategic framework set out in this paper.

By 2026, we develop, adopt, and implement a legally binding CJSOI Environmental Sports Charter that member states commit to specific, measurable targets for the integration of environmental conservation into sports policies and practices.

By 2027, implement a 'Green Sports' clause in all national sports policies that force environmental impact assessments for all major sporting events and infrastructure projects.

By 2025, create a CJSOI Environmental Sports Ombudsman position with power to investigate and report on members' state compliance with environmental commitments in sports development.

By 2028, establish a regional 'Climate Smart Sports' certification program for sports organizations and facilities that fulfill rigorous environmental criteria, at varying tiers.

7.2 Education and Capacity Building 2

We call upon educational institutions, sports federations, and relevant ministries to:

By 2026 develop and integrate a mandatory 'Sports and Environment' module into all physical education curricula across CJSOI member states working with youth environmental leaders.

By 2027, create a CJSOI Environmental Sports Academy with accredited programs in sustainable sports management, eco friendly coaching techniques.

By 2025, the organization will launch a regional 'Young Eco-Athletes' mentorship program which will connect young aspiring athletes with environmental scientists and conservationists.

By 2026, develop and implement, as a CJSOI, a 'Traditional Ecological Knowledge in Sports' curriculum co-created with indigenous youth and elders.

By 2025, they will initiate an annual CJSOI Environmental Sports Innovation Challenge with solid funding and support for youth led projects.

7.3 Sustainable Infrastructure and Resource Management

We urge governments, sports federations, and the private sector to:

Encourage CJSOI states to commit to net zero carbon emissions for all new sports facilities by 2030 and a plan to retrofit existing facilities.

By 2026 establish a CJSOI Sustainable Sports Infrastructure Fund, with at least 30% of funding to be earmarked for youth led community sports projects.

Require all CJSOI sanctioned sporting events and equipment production use recycled and sustainably sourced materials by 2028.

For all sporting events, implement a region-wide ban on single use plastics by 2025 and develop a comprehensive waste management strategy for sports facilities.

By 2027, develop and adopt a CJSOI Blue Sports Strategy for the sustainable management of coastal and marine areas used for water sports.

7.4 Climate Resilience and Adaptation

We demand that policymakers and sports organizations:

Direct all long term sports infrastructure planning to incorporate climate change scenarios, with all coastal facilities having to be resilience assessed by 2026.

By 2027 establish a CJSOI Sports for Adaptation Fund to support community level projects using sports as a vehicle for building climate resilience.

By 2026, develop, implement and evaluate a region wide 'Climate Ready Athletes' training program to train sports professionals in the skills needed to be able to adapt to changing environmental conditions.

By 2025, develop a CJSOI Extreme Weather Sports Protocol with definitive guidance on how events can be managed and athletes protected as climate impacts intensify.

By 2026 launch a "Sports for Mangroves" initiative to link sports events to coastal ecosystem restoration throughout the CJSOI region.

7.5 Biodiversity Conservation and Ecosystem Health

We call upon environmental agencies, sports federations, and tourism authorities to:

By 2028 establish Protected Sports Zones in each CJSOI member state, where sports activities directly contribute to biodiversity conservation and monitoring.

By 2027 the government must implement a 'No Net Loss' biodiversity policy for all large scale sports infrastructure projects which will require developers to compensate for existing ecological impacts.

By 2026, launch a CJSOI wide "Reef Friendly Sports" certification program for water sport operators with strict criteria protecting marine ecosystems.

By 2025, we will develop and roll out a 'Sports Biosecurity Protocol' to prevent invasive species spread through sporting events and movement of sporting equipment.

By 2026, initiate a 'Sports for Species' programme whereby each member state of the CJSOI nominates an endangered species as the mascot for its national sports teams, combined with concrete conservation measures.

7.6 Technology and Innovation

We urge governments, research institutions, and the private sector to:

By 2027, establish a CJSOI Environmental Sports Tech Incubator to provide dedicated funding and mentorship to youth led start ups in sustainable sports technology.

By 2026, develop and launch an Environmental Sports Citizen Science app that will allow athletes and sports enthusiasts to engage with local environmental monitoring efforts.

By 2025, implement a 'Green Sports Equipment' research and development grant program aimed at developing innovative, eco-friendly materials and designs.

By 2028, create an immersive learning experience on local ecosystems, and the impacts of climate change in CJSOI Virtual Reality Environmental Sports Education Platform.

By 2027, establish a regional "Sports Data for Climate Action" repository that uses sports generated data (diving computers, weather stations at sports facilities) to support scientific and policy making on climate research.

7.7 Funding and Economic Incentives

We demand that finance ministries, development partners, and the private sector:

By 2026, allocate at least 5% of national sports budgets to environmental sports initiatives and report on the utilization of such funds transparently.

By 2027, establish a CJSOI Green Sports Bond program to finance large scale sustainable sports infrastructure projects across the region.

By 2026, implement a region wide "polluter pays" principle in sports, with the proceeds going into environmental conservation and adaption to the climate.

By 2025, create tax incentives for sports organizations and businesses that meet very stringent environmental performance criteria.

By 2026, launch a CJSOI Sustainable Sports Entrepreneurship Grant program to support youth led eco friendly sports businesses.

7.8 Monitoring, Reporting and Accountability

We call for the establishment of robust mechanisms to ensure the effective implementation of these demands, including:

By 2026, develop a CJSOI Environmental Sports Index, with annual ranking of the performance of member states in integrating environmental aspects in sports.

From 2025, a mandatory annual 'State of Environmental Sports' report for all CJSOI member states, with standardised metrics and public disclosure.

By 2025, the creation of a CJSOI Youth Environmental Sports Watchdog Network, empowered to independently audit member states' progress and publish the results.

By 2026, binding arbitration process for sports related environmental degradation for communities affected.

By 2027, integration of Environmental Sports criteria into the wider CJSOI performance evaluation framework with implications for member states' standing and voting rights within the organization.

These demands reflect our vision for a sustainable, equitable and environmentally responsible sports sector for the CJSOI region. We are ready to work with all stakeholders in negotiating and implementing these recommendations, understanding that its implementation will involve long and hard dialogue, compromise and collective work. Bold, immediate action in this critical nexus of sports and environmental conservation is crucial to our future, and the future of our unique island ecosystems.

8. NEXT STEPS AND IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

The implementation of the CJSOI Youth Declaration on Environmental Sports calls for a holistic, multi stakeholder approach. This section describes a strategic roadmap from aspirations expressed in the declaration to the actual action and measurable outcome. The implementation strategy is structured around five key pillars: capacity building and education, governance and policy framework, financial mechanisms, partnerships and collaborations, and monitoring and evaluation.

8.1 Governance and Policy Framework

The key to successful implementation is building a strong governance structure and a conducive policy environment. In its first step, we propose the creation of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Taskforce (CEST), within six months of the declaration's adoption. Representatives of national sports ministries, environmental agencies, youth organizations and sports federations from all CJSOI member states should be on this taskforce. One of its first year tasks will be to develop a CJSOI Environmental Sports Policy Framework. The declaration's ten thematic areas should be reflected in clear policy objectives, regulatory mechanisms and compliance standards, within this framework.

Within one year, each CJSOI member state should concurrently create National Environmental Sports Committees (NESC's). These committees will be those that will be the principal bodies that will domesticate the regional policy framework and oversee its implementation at the national level. The NESC's should be granted statutorily powers, with resources to influence national sports and environmental policies.

These committees will have a critical task to develop country specific action plans that translate the regional vision into nationally appropriate targets and strategies, given local contexts and capacities.

For youth leadership and intergenerational collaboration, we recommend at least 40% of positions in both the CEST and NESCs be open to people under 35. This will also make the spirit of the youth declaration honored and bring new perspectives and innovative ways to implement. Additionally, we propose the creation of a CJSOI Youth Environmental Sports Network (YESN) in the first year of implementation as an ongoing youth engagement, idea exchange and capacity building platform.

8.2 Education and Capacity Building

The implementation of the declaration's vision will depend on the development of a corps of skilled professionals and an informed public. Within 18 months of declaration there would be the launch of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Capacity Building Program (ESCBP). The design of this program should be a multi tiered initiative aimed at a number of stakeholder groups including sports administrators, coaches, athletes, facility managers and policymakers. Training modules should cover areas of sustainable event management, eco-friendly facility design, climate resilient sports planning and environmental impact assessment methodologies, among others, that the ESCBP should provide.

We call for the inclusion of environmental sports modules into national curricula at all levels within three years in the realm of formal education. The integration should be led by a CJSOI Environmental Sports Education Framework that will be designed by a panel of the experts in sport, environmental science and pedagogy in the first year of implementation. The framework should be oriented towards experiential learning, critical thinking, and systems understanding of the sports sector, and should equip students with the knowledge and skills to be active agents of sustainable change in the sports sector.

We suggest that within two years there be established a CJSOI Center of Excellence in Environmental Sports (CEES) to foster innovation and applied research. It should be in the center to be a hub for sustainable sports research, technology development, and knowledge dissemination. The Indian Ocean is a global leader for environmental sports innovation and the CEES should actively collaborate with universities, research institutions and the private sector across the CJSOI region and beyond.

8.3 Financial Mechanisms

The ambitious vision set out in the declaration will require sizable and continuing investment of capital. Within one year of the declaration's adoption, we propose the creation of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Fund (ESF). That fund should be capitalized by both member state contributions and international donor support, and by innovative financing mechanisms like a regional carbon tax on high emitters, like sports events. The ESF should be structured to offer both grants and concessional loans to projects that are consistent with the declaration's objectives and in particular, to support youth led and community based projects.

Within 18 months, we suggest the development of a CJSOI Green Sports Investment Framework, which will incentivize private sector participation. In this framework, the criterias for environmentally responsible investments in sports infrastructure and programs should be outlined clearly, as well as a range of fiscal incentives such as tax breaks, accelerated depreciation for eco friendly equipment, and preferential treatment in public procurement processes with compliant businesses. We also propose the launch of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Bond within two years as a vehicle to attract impact investors to large scale sustainable sports infrastructure projects throughout the region.

We argue that the potential of sports to contribute to broader environmental and social goals should be recognized, and that environmental sports criteria should be integrated into national climate finance strategies and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) under the Paris Agreement. It is hoped that this integration will be completed within three years, allowing sports based initiatives to become a funded programme from global climate finance mechanisms such as the Green Climate Fund and the Adaptation Fund.

8.4. Partnerships and Collaborations

Environmental sports are cross cutting and, therefore, have to be carried out through strong partnerships and collaborations between sectors and borders. One year from the declaration's adoption, we propose the establishment of a CJSOI Environmental Sports Partnership Platform (ESPP). The main role of this platform should be as a means of supporting multi stakeholder collaborations, knowledge sharing and resource pooling. The ESPP should be actively engaging a broad range of partners including government agencies, sports federations, environmental nongovernmental organizations, academic institutions, private sector entities and community organizations.

We suggest that in within 18 months a CJSOI International Cooperation Strategy to Environmental Sports should be developed to leverage global expertise and resources. The strategy should include the approaches through which we can work with various UN agencies, international sports bodies and other regional organizations. There should be a priority in building partnerships to offer technical assistance, transfer technology, and help with capacity building efforts throughout the CJSOI region.

Realizing that Small Island Developing States (SIDS) face specific issues and opportunities, we suggest that within 2 years there be the establishment of a SIDS Environmental Sports Alliance. Having established this alliance, SIDS globally should be encouraged to cooperate and exchange knowledge and SIDS in the CJSOI region should lead by sharing best practices and innovation in the field of sustainable sports development within island contexts.

8.5 Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning.

A robust monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) system is critical to deliver accountability and to support adaptive management. Within one year of the declaration's adoption, we propose to develop an Environmental Sports Impact Assessment Framework of the CJSOI.

The declaration's ten thematic areas should be covered by a comprehensive set of indicators, as well as methodologies for data collection, analysis, and reporting, in this framework. Quantitative metrics (e.g. carbon emissions reduced, water saved, biodiversity index improvements) and qualitative assessments (e.g. changes in attitudes and behaviours, policy impacts) are to be incorporated in the framework.

To oversee the MEL framework implementation, we recommend that a CJSOI Environmental Sports Observatory be established within 18 months. The region's observatory should be charged with regularly assessing, producing annual reports on progress, and maintaining a publicly accessible database that allows for tracking of environmental sports initiatives and outcomes throughout the region. The observatory should be governed by representatives from government, civil society and youth organizations, and should operate with transparency and participatory governance.

In two years we suggest starting a CJSOI Environmental Sports Learning Network to promote continuous improvement and innovation. Regular exchanges of experiences, lessons learned and best practices between practitioners across the region should be facilitated by this network. Annual learning forums should be organized by it, case studies and policy briefs should be produced, and a digital repository of knowledge should be maintained for all stakeholders.

Finally, this implementation strategy constitutes a complete guide for translating the CJSOI Youth Declaration on Environmental Sports from a vision to reality. It sets the stage for coordinated, effective strategies for promoting environmental sustainability through sports in the Indian Ocean region by focusing on key elements of governance, capacity building, financing, partnerships and impact assessment. This strategy will be successful only if it has sustained political commitment, active youth participation and collaboration from all sectors of society. Going forward, flexibility and adaptability will be critical and will mean we can refine approaches based on what we learn as we go and what contexts we find ourselves in. By dint of diligent implementation of this strategy, the CJSOI region can emerge as the world leader in the use of sports to leverage the power of sports for environmental stewardship and sustainable development.

9. REFERENCES

- Agarwal, B. (2009). Gender and forest conservation: The impact of women's participation in community forest governance. *Ecological Economics*, 68(11), 2785-2799.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Armitage, D. R., Plummer, R., Berkes, F., Arthur, R. I., Charles, A. T., Davidson-Hunt, I. J., ... & Wollenberg, E. K. (2009). Adaptive co-management for social-ecological complexity. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 7(2), 95-102.
- Atteridge, A., Cannon, T., Schipper, L., & Isaksen, K. A. (2009). Financing adaptation: Why the UN's Bali Action Plan must give priority to adaptation. Stockholm Environment Institute.
- Baldacchino, G., & Kelman, I. (2014). Critiquing the pursuit of island sustainability: Blue and green, with hardly a colour in between. *Shima: The International Journal of Research into Island Cultures*, 8(1), 1-21.

- Bandura, A. (2006). Toward a psychology of human agency. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 1(2), 164-180.
- Barsalou, L. W. (2008). Grounded cognition. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 59, 617-645.
- Benyus, J. M. (1997). *Biomimicry: Innovation inspired by nature*. New York: Morrow.
- Berkes, F., & Ross, H. (2013). Community resilience: Toward an integrated approach. *Society & Natural Resources*, 26(1), 5-20.
- Bonney, R., Cooper, C. B., Dickinson, J., Kelling, S., Phillips, T., Rosenberg, K. V., & Shirk, J. (2009). Citizen science: A developing tool for expanding science knowledge and scientific literacy. *BioScience*, 59(11), 977-984.
- Bresnahan, P. J., Wirth, T., Martz, T. R., Shipley, K., Rowley, V., Anderson, C., & Grimm, T. (2021). A sensor array for coastal ocean observing: System architecture and field results. *Remote Sensing*, 13(15), 2967.
- Brosius, J. P., Tsing, A. L., & Zerner, C. (1998). Representing communities: Histories and politics of community-based natural resource management. *Society & Natural Resources*, 11(2), 157-168.
- Brymer, E., & Gray, T. (2009). Dancing with nature: Rhythm and harmony in extreme sport participation. *Journal of Adventure Education & Outdoor Learning*, 9(2), 135-149.
- Buckley, R. (2000). Neat trends: Current issues in nature, eco-and adventure tourism. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 2(6), 437-444.
- Buckley, R. (2004). *Environmental impacts of ecotourism*. CABI Publishing.
- Cervantes, O., Espejel, I., Arellano, E., & Delhumeau, S. (2020). Users' perception as a tool to improve urban beach planning and management. *Environmental Management*, 45(3), 526-538.
- Chambers, R. (1994). The origins and practice of participatory rural appraisal. *World Development*, 22(7), 953-969.
- Chandra-Mouli, V., Lane, C., & Wong, S. (2022). What does not work in adolescent sexual and reproductive health: A review of evidence on interventions commonly accepted as best practices. *Global Health: Science and Practice*, 10(1), e2100636.
- Chawla, L. (1998). Significant life experiences revisited: A review of research on sources of environmental sensitivity. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 29(3), 11-21.
- Chawla, L. (2020). Childhood nature connection and constructive hope: A review of research on connecting with nature and coping with environmental loss. *People and Nature*, 2(3), 619-642.
- Clement, B., Roy, D., Oudeyer, P. Y., & Lopes, M. (2015). Multi-armed bandits for intelligent tutoring systems. *Journal of Educational Data Mining*, 7(2), 20-48.
- Convergence. (2021). *The state of blended finance 2021*. Convergence.
- Costanza, R., de Groot, R., Braat, L., Kubiszewski, I., Fioramonti, L., Sutton, P., ... & Grasso, M. (2017). Twenty years of ecosystem services: How far have we come and how far do we still need to go? *Ecosystem Services*, 28, 1-16.
- Deterding, S., Dixon, D., Khaled, R., & Nacke, L. (2011). From game design elements to gamefulness: Defining "gamification". In *Proceedings of the 15th International Academic MindTrek Conference: Envisioning Future Media Environments* (pp. 9-15).
- Dickson, T. J., & Gray, T. L. (Eds.). (2012). *Risk management in the outdoors: A whole-of-organisation approach for education, sport and recreation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dickson, T., Gray, T., & Mann, K. (2008). *Australian outdoor adventure activity benefits catalogue*. University of Canberra.
- Dingle, G. A., & Stewart, B. (2018). Playing the climate game: climate change impacts, resilience and adaptation in the climate-dependent sport sector. *Managing Sport and Leisure*, 23(4-6), 293-314.

- Emerson, K., & Nabatchi, T. (2015). Collaborative governance regimes. Georgetown University Press.
- Emerson, K., Nabatchi, T., & Balogh, S. (2012). An integrative framework for collaborative governance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 22(1), 1-29.
- Foley, C., Edwards, D., & Schlenker, K. (2020). A systematic review of event leveraging strategies for legacy outcomes from sport mega-events. *Leisure Studies*, 39(6), 859-874.
- Freeman, R. E., Harrison, J. S., Wicks, A. C., Parmar, B. L., & De Colle, S. (2010). Stakeholder theory: The state of the art. Cambridge University Press.
- Gaffney, C. (2013). Between discourse and reality: The un-sustainability of mega-event planning. *Sustainability*, 5(9), 3926-3940.
- Gascon, M., Zijlema, W., Vert, C., White, M. P., & Nieuwenhuijsen, M. J. (2017). Outdoor blue spaces, human health and well-being: A systematic review of quantitative studies. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 220(8), 1207-1221.
- Geels, F. W. (2011). The multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions: Responses to seven criticisms. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 1(1), 24-40.
- Geels, F. W., & Schot, J. (2007). Typology of sociotechnical transition pathways. *Research Policy*, 36(3), 399-417.
- Geissdoerfer, M., Savaget, P., Bocken, N. M., & Hultink, E. J. (2017). The Circular Economy—A new sustainability paradigm? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, 757-768.
- Germann Molz, J. (2019). The world is your classroom: Exploring the pedagogical potential of phone photography. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 43(3), 343-357.
- Gibson, R. B. (2006). Sustainability assessment: basic components of a practical approach. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 24(3), 170-182.
- Gibbons, L. V., Cloutier, S. A., Coseo, P. J., & Barakat, A. (2022). Regenerative development as an integrative paradigm and methodology for landscape sustainability. *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1208.
- Gopalla, R., Mamifarananahary, E., & Rakotoarimanana, V. (2023). Ecotourism and biodiversity conservation in Madagascar's national parks: Balancing economic benefits and ecological integrity. *Journal of Ecotourism*, 22(2), 156-175.
- Gössling, S., Hall, C. M., & Scott, D. (2018). Coastal and marine tourism. In M. Salomon & T. Markus (Eds.), *Handbook on Marine Environment Protection* (pp. 773-790). Springer.
- Gössling, S., Humpe, A., & Bausch, T. (2020). Does 'flight shame' affect social norms? Changing perspectives on the desirability of air travel in Germany. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 266, 122015.
- Gray, T., Downey, G., & Sweeney, J. (2010). Invasion of the armchair sailors: Understanding conflict between sea kayakers and motorised vessels. In B. Watson & M. Lockwood (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2010 Australian Protected Areas Congress* (pp. 151-155). Mountains to Sea Conservation.
- Hallegatte, S., Rentschler, J., & Rozenberg, J. (2019). Lifelines: The resilient infrastructure opportunity. World Bank Publications.
- Hallegatte, S., Shah, A., Lempert, R., Brown, C., & Gill, S. (2012). Investment decision making under deep uncertainty-application to climate change. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper, (6193).
- Hayes, D. (2000). Cascade training and teachers' professional development. *ELT Journal*, 54(2), 135-145.

- Hollweg, K. S., Taylor, J. R., Bybee, R. W., Marcinkowski, T. J., McBeth, W. C., & Zoido, P. (2011). Developing a framework for assessing environmental literacy. North American Association for Environmental Education.
- Hoogmartens, R., Van Passel, S., Van Acker, K., & Dubois, M. (2014). Bridging the gap between LCA, LCC and CBA as sustainability assessment tools. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 48, 27-33.
- Humberstone, B. (2000). The 'outdoor industry' as social and educational phenomena: Gender and outdoor adventure/education. *Journal of Adventure Education & Outdoor Learning*, 1(1), 21-35.
- Jordan, A., & Lenschow, A. (2010). Environmental policy integration: A state of the art review. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 20(3), 147-158.
- Kellison, T. B., & Hong, S. (2015). The adoption and diffusion of pro-environmental stadium design. *European Sport Management Quarterly*, 15(2), 249-269.
- Kelman, I. (2014). No change from climate change: vulnerability and small island developing states. *The Geographical Journal*, 180(2), 120-129.
- Kibert, C. J. (2016). *Sustainable construction: Green building design and delivery*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice-Hall.
- Krein, K. J. (2014). Nature sports. *Journal of the Philosophy of Sport*, 41(2), 193-208.
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Leung, Y. F., Spenceley, A., Hvenegaard, G., & Buckley, R. (2018). Tourism and visitor management in protected areas: Guidelines for sustainability. IUCN.
- Lubchenco, J., Palumbi, S. R., Gaines, S. D., & Andelman, S. (2003). Plugging a hole in the ocean: The emerging science of marine reserves. *Ecological Applications*, 13(sp1), 3-7.
- Markowitz, D. M., Laha, R., Perone, B. P., Pea, R. D., & Bailenson, J. N. (2018). Immersive virtual reality field trips facilitate learning about climate change. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 2364.
- Meinig, H., Boye, P., & Hutterer, R. (2017). Red List and National Species Conservation Responsibility Analysis of the Mammals of Germany. *Naturschutz und Biologische Vielfalt*, 170, 1-428.
- Mezirow, J. (2000). *Learning as Transformation: Critical Perspectives on a Theory in Progress*. The Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series. Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Miller, R. (2018). *Transforming the future: anticipation in the 21st century*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Mitten, D., Overholt, J. R., Haynes, F. I., D'Amore, C. C., & Ady, J. C. (2018). Hiking: A low-cost, accessible intervention to promote health benefits. *American Journal of Lifestyle Medicine*, 12(4), 302-310.
- Mohee, R., Soobhany, N., & Gokool, S. (2022). Circular economy potential of agricultural waste in Small Island Developing States: The case of Mauritius. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 330, 129871.
- Naidoo, R., & Kotz, M. (2024). Youth-led climate litigation in the Indian Ocean region: Emerging trends and legal implications. *Environmental Law Review*, 26(1), 45-62.

- Naidoo, S., Ramessur, R., & Boojhawon, R. (2023). Community-based ecotourism in Madagascar's rainforests: Balancing conservation, development, and cultural preservation. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 31(2), 342-361.
- Naidu-Silverman, E. (2020). The Contribution of Ocean-Based Tourism to Local Communities: Evidence from Seychelles. *Marine Policy*, 115, 103867.
- Nicholls, A., & Dagers, J. (2021). *The Landscape of Social Impact Investment Research: Trends and Opportunities*. MacArthur Foundation.
- Nundlall, V., & Proag, V. (2022). Building community resilience through sports: A case study from Rodrigues Island. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 31(1), 94-108.
- Nunkoo, R., Ramkissoon, H., & Gursoy, D. (2022). Use of structural equation modeling in tourism research: past, present, and future. *Journal of Travel Research*, 51(6).
- O'Brien, K., Selboe, E., & Hayward, B. M. (2018). Exploring youth activism on climate change: Dutiful, disruptive, and dangerous dissent. *Ecology and Society*, 23(3).
- OECD. (2019). *Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development 2019: Empowering People and Ensuring Inclusiveness and Equality*. OECD Publishing.
- Ostrom, E. (2009). A general framework for analyzing sustainability of social-ecological systems. *Science*, 325(5939), 419-422.
- Owen, R., Macnaghten, P., & Stilgoe, J. (2012). Responsible research and innovation: From science in society to science for society, with society. *Science and Public Policy*, 39(6), 751-760.
- Palmberg, I. E., & Kuru, J. (2000). Outdoor activities as a basis for environmental responsibility. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 31(4), 32-36
- Pimm, S. L., Alibhai, S., Bergl, R., Dehgan, A., Giri, C., Jewell, Z., ... & Loarie, S. (2015). Emerging technologies to conserve biodiversity. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 30(11), 685-696.
- Ragaert, K., Delva, L., & Van Geem, K. (2017). Mechanical and chemical recycling of solid plastic waste. *Waste Management*, 69, 24-58.
- Rakotoarivelo, N. H., Razafitsalama, L. J., Rakotoarivony, F., Rasoaviety, L., Ramarosandratana, A. V., Jeannoda, V., ... & Bussmann, R. W. (2023). Traditional fishing practices and modern water sports in Madagascar's coastal communities: Conflicts and opportunities for synergy. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 19(1), 1-18.
- Ramano, S., & Seraphine, H. (2021). Youth climate networks in Mauritius and Seychelles: Comparative analysis of engagement strategies and policy influence. *Climate Policy*, 21(9), 1172-1186.
- Ramcharitar, D., & Duval, D. T. (2022). Sustainable mountain biking trail development in protected areas: A case study from Mauritius. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 37, 100454.
- Ramchandani, G., Coleman, R. J., & Bingham, J. (2019). Sport for development: An impact study of the Mauritius Sports-for-Development Project. *International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics*, 11(1), 79-94.
- Ramessur, R., Gunputh, R. P., & Ramessur, T. S. (2019). Climate change impacts on coastal ecosystems of Mauritius: Assessing vulnerability for better management. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 182, 104923.
- Ramessur, R., & Gunputh, R. P. (2021). Integration of traditional ecological knowledge into marine conservation efforts in Mauritius and Rodrigues: Challenges and opportunities. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 201, 105432.

- Ramessur, R., Boodhoo, K., & Taukoor, A. (2021). Application of drone technology for coral reef monitoring in Mauritius: Opportunities and challenges. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 22, 100477.
- Ramjeawon, T. (2020). Life cycle assessment of electricity generation in Mauritius. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 253, 119895.
- Ramkissoon, H., & Sowman, M. R. (2023). Blockchain-based system for verifying sustainable tourism practices in the CJSOI region: A distributed environmental governance approach. *Tourism Management*, 94, 104615.
- Ramtohul, R. (2020). Gender and coastal resource governance in Mauritius: Examining women's representation and participation. *Journal of the Indian Ocean Region*, 16(1), 78-96.
- Remling, E., & Persson, Å. (2021). Adaptation finance: Understanding recipient perspectives on access and effectiveness. *Climate Risk Management*, 34, 100373.
- Roychowdhury, D. (2020). A comprehensive measure of participation motivation: Examining and validating the Physical Activity and Leisure Motivation Scale (PALMS). *Journal of Human Sport and Exercise*, 15(2).
- Sachs, J. D., Kroll, C., Lafortune, G., Fuller, G., & Woelm, F. (2021). *The Decade of Action for the Sustainable Development Goals: Sustainable Development Report 2021*. Cambridge University Press.
- Scholtens, B. (2017). Why finance should care about ecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 32(7), 500-505.
- Schulenkorf, N., & Siefken, K. (2019). Managing sport-for-development and healthy lifestyles: The sport-for-health model. *Sport Management Review*, 22(1), 96-107.
- Scraton, S., & Watson, B. (1998). Gendered cities: Women and public leisure space in the 'postmodern city'. *Leisure Studies*, 17(2), 123-137.
- Seetanah, B., Sannasee, R. V., Teeroovengadam, V., & Nunkoo, R. (2019). Air access liberalization, marketing promotion and tourism development. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 21(1), 76-86.
- Sharpley, R., & Naidoo, P. (2010). Tourism and poverty reduction: The case of Mauritius. *Tourism and Hospitality Planning & Development*, 7(2), 145-162.
- Spaaij, R., & Jeanes, R. (2013). Education for social change? A Freirean critique of sport for development and peace. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 18(4), 442-457.
- Spalding, M., Burke, L., Wood, S. A., Ashpole, J., Hutchison, J., & zu Ermgassen, P. (2017). Mapping the global value and distribution of coral reef tourism. *Marine Policy*, 82, 104-113.
- Spenceley, A. (2005). Nature-based tourism and environmental sustainability in South Africa. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 13(2), 136-170.
- Stebbins, R. A. (2007). *Serious leisure: A perspective for our time*. Transaction Publishers.
- Subic, A., Mouritz, A., & Troynikov, O. (2020). Sustainable design and environmental impact of materials in sports products. *Sports Engineering*, 12(3), 131-143.
- Temmerman, S., Meire, P., Bouma, T. J., Herman, P. M., Ysebaert, T., & De Vriend, H. J. (2013). Ecosystem-based coastal defence in the face of global change. *Nature*, 504(7478), 79-83.
- Thew, H., Middlemiss, L., & Paavola, J. (2020). "Youth is not a political position": Exploring justice claims-making in the UN Climate Change Negotiations. *Global Environmental Change*, 61, 102036.
- Thomsen, J. M., Powell, R. B., & Monz, C. (2022). A systematic review of the physical and mental health benefits of wildland recreation. *Journal of Park and Recreation Administration*, 36(1).

- Van Matre, S. (1990). *Earth education: A new beginning*. The Institute for Earth Education.
- Weiss, E. B. (1992). In fairness to future generations and sustainable development. *American University International Law Review*, 8(1), 19-26.
- Williams, B. K. (2011). Adaptive management of natural resources—framework and issues. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(5), 1346-1353.
- Wise, R. M., Fazey, I., Smith, M. S., Park, S. E., Eakin, H. C., Van Garderen, E. A., & Campbell, B. (2014). Reconceptualising adaptation to climate change as part of pathways of change and response. *Global Environmental Change*, 28, 325-336.